

Pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides and 2-phosphaindolizines

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Abstract : New 2-phosphaindolizines have been prepared and characterized. The formation of six new pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides was detected by ^{31}P NMR spectroscopy. Six pyridinium salts were prepared and characterized spectroscopically.

Keywords : 2-Phosphaindolizine, pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylide, 1,5-electrocyclization, ^{31}P NMR.

Introduction

Reagents bearing a dihalophosphino moiety, particularly the dichlorophosphino moiety, are important synthons that have been used for the synthesis of a variety of organophosphorus compounds¹⁻³. The dichlorophosphino substituted ylides are ambident species and can react with electrophilic as well as nucleophilic reagents.

In the formation of 2-phosphaindolizines from the [4+1] cyclocondensation of 1,2-dialkylpyridinium bromides with phosphorus trichloride in the presence of triethylamine, a stable intermediate, pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylide, was first isolated⁴. Subsequently, differently substituted pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides were obtained from the dichlorophosphinylation of pyridinium methylides generated *in situ*⁵. In the case of 2-unsubstituted pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides, it was found that these intermediates when left in solution, changed into 1,3-bis(alkoxycarbonyl)-2-phosphaindolizines⁶. The formation of the latter could be explained on the basis of a reorganization of pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides to produce the intermediate bis(pyridiniumylidyl)phosphenium chloride followed by its intramolecular 1,5-electrocyclization and 1,2-elimination⁷. The reorganization of the pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides is similar to that of triphenylphosphonium dichlorophosphinomethylides⁸. The intermediate, bis(pyridiniumylidyl)phosphenium chloride, could also be produced from the reaction of pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides with pyridinium methylides gener-

ated *in situ*, leading to the development of a facile one-pot synthesis of 1,3-bis(alkoxycarbonyl)-2-phosphaindolizines^{6,7}. This methodology could be extended to the synthesis of 1,3-azaphospholo[5,1-*a*]isoquinolines also⁹. Following a similar method, we report here the formation of some new pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides and 1,3-bis(alkoxycarbonyl)-2-phosphaindolizines.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides :

N-(Alkoxycarbonylmethyl)pyridinium bromides (**1**) on reaction with phosphorus trichloride (1 equiv.) and triethylamine (2 equiv.) in toluene in a nitrogen atmosphere were found to form pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides, **2a-f** (Scheme 1).

The formation of pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides was indicated by a ^{31}P NMR signal in the range δ 132.5–149.6¹⁰; however, these intermediates could not be isolated in a pure state as they start changing into the corresponding 2-phosphaindolizines (δ ^{31}P ~ 179).

Synthesis of 2-phosphaindolizines :

N-(Alkoxycarbonylmethyl)pyridinium bromides (**1**) (2 equiv.) on reaction with phosphorus trichloride (1 equiv.) and triethylamine (4 equiv.) in methylene chloride in a nitrogen atmosphere lead to the initial formation of *N*-pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides **2**, which subsequently changed into 2-phosphaindolizines **3** (δ ^{31}P ~ 179) through reorganization followed by successive intramolecular 1,5-electrocyclization and 1,2-elimination (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

2-Phosphaindolizine **3a** could be separated as yellow crystalline solid, but **3b** was obtained as a sticky mass. The phosphaindolizines **3c-f**, however, could not be isolated, although their formation was indicated by a ³¹P NMR signal at δ ~ 179. In the case of **2c,d**, a complex mixture having several ³¹P NMR signals was obtained, as the acetoxy (**2c**)/hydroxyl (**2d**) group in the pyridine ring induced some side reactions. On the other hand, **3e,f** having dimethylamino group could not be separated from the ammonium salt, probably due to the formation of phosphaindolizine salt as a result of the capture of a proton by NMe₂ group. The compounds **3a,b** could be well characterized by their ³¹P and ¹H NMR chemical shifts.

Experimental

The starting materials, namely substituted pyridines and alkyl bromoacetates were purchased from Aldrich and used as such. Phosphorus trichloride (Merck) and triethylamine (Merck) were freshly distilled under nitrogen atmosphere before use. Solvents (diethyl ether, methylene chloride and toluene) were distilled and dried by common methods. All experiments were done under ni-

trogen atmosphere using Schlenk technique. Melting points were determined by the capillary method and are uncorrected. NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL FX 90Q spectrometer (³¹P NMR at 36.23 MHz; ¹H NMR at 89.55 MHz). The chemical shifts refer to 85% H₃PO₄ as an external reference for ³¹P NMR and TMS as an internal reference for ¹H NMR.

N-(Alkoxycarbonylmethyl)pyridinium bromides **1a-f** : General method :

To a solution of a substituted pyridine (50 mmol) in diethyl ether (100 mL) was added an equimolar amount of alkyl bromoacetate with constant stirring at room temperature (~ 25 °C). After stirring the mixture for 10–12 days, a white to cream coloured solid formed, which was filtered off, washed with dry ether (2 × 25 mL) and dried under vacuum.

In the case of **1c** and **1d**, initially formed oils changed to solid on maceration with methylene chloride. In **1d**, ¹H NMR reveals the hydrolysis of the acetoxy group to a hydroxy group during preparation.

Note

(1a) : Yield 67%, m.p. 158–160 °C (Found : C, 46.37; H, 5.21; N, 5.26. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₄NO₂Br (260.13) : C, 46.13; H, 5.42; N, 5.38%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 1.31 (3H, t, *J* 8.5 Hz, 4-CH₂CH₃), 2.97 (2H, q, *J* 8.5 Hz, 4-CH₂CH₃), 3.74 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.30 (2H, s, NCH₂), 7.86 (2H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, 3-H and 5-H), 9.41 (2H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, 2-H and 6-H).

(1b) : Yield 73%, m.p. 156–158 °C (Found : C, 48.42; H, 5.81; N, 5.03. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₆NO₂Br (274.15) : C, 48.19; H, 5.88; N, 5.10%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 1.24 (3H, t, *J* 8.5 Hz, 4-CH₂CH₃), 1.30 (3H, t, *J* 8.5 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 2.90 (2H, q, *J* 8.5 Hz, 4-CH₂CH₃), 4.18 (2H, q, *J* 8.5 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 6.0 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 7.71 (2H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, 5-H and 3-H), 9.22 (2H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, 2-H and 6-H).

(1c) : Yield 48%, m.p. 137–139 °C (Found : C, 41.58; H, 4.21; N, 4.73. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₂NO₄Br (290.11) : C, 41.40; H, 4.17; N, 4.83%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO, δ ppm) : 2.34 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.91 (2H, s, NCH₂), 7.92 (1H, dd, *J* 6.9, 8.3 Hz, 5-H), 8.16 (1H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz, 4-H), 8.90 (1H, s, 6-H), 9.39 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 2-H).

(1d) : Yield 25%, m.p. 140–143 °C (Found : C, 41.42; H, 4.48; N, 5.39. Calcd. for C₉H₁₂NO₃Br (262.10) : C, 41.24; H, 4.61; N, 5.34%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO, δ ppm) : 1.20 (3H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 2.30 (broad singlet, OH), 4.30 (2H, q, *J* 6.7 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 5.63 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 7.26 (1H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz, 5-H), 7.71 (1H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, 4-H), 8.28 (1H, s, 2-H), 8.33 (1H, d, ³*J*_{HH} 6.9 Hz, 6-H).

(1e) : Yield 98%, m.p. 228–230 °C (Found : C, 43.79; H, 5.41; N, 10.26. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₅N₂O₂Br (275.14) : C, 43.65; H, 5.49; N, 10.18%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO, δ ppm) : 3.32 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH₂), 5.42 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 6.97 (2H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, 3-H and 5-H), 8.49 (2H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, 2-H and 6-H).

(1f) : Yield 96%, m.p. 222–223 °C (Found : C, 45.37; H, 5.81; N, 9.62. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₇N₂O₂Br (289.17) : C, 45.69; H, 5.92; N, 9.69%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 1.17 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.06 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 3.96 (2H, q, *J* 6.9 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 5.25 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 6.60 (2H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, 3-H and 5-H), 8.40 (2H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, 2-H and 6-H).

Pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides 2a-f : General method :

The *N*-alkylpyridinium bromide (1) (10 mmol) was suspended in toluene (30 mL) and triethylamine (20 mmol, 2.0 g, 2.8 mL) was added slowly with stirring at room temperature whereupon a light yellow colour developed. After stirring the reaction mixture for 10–15 min, a solution of phosphorus trichloride (10 mmol, 1.36 g, 0.9 mL) in toluene (10 mL) was added slowly with continuous stirring. The progress of the reaction was monitored by ³¹P NMR spectroscopy. A ³¹P NMR signal at δ 132.5–149.3 indicated the formation of pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides^{6,7}, which, however, start changing into 2-phosphaindolizines and hence could not be isolated.

δ ³¹P NMR (Toluene) : (2a) : 149.0, (2b) : 149.3, (2c) : 146.0, (2d) : 146.2, (2e) : 132.5, (2f) : 133.5.

1,3-Azaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines (3a,b) :

The *N*-(alkoxycarbonylmethyl)pyridinium bromide (20 mmol, 1a, 5.20 g; 1b, 5.48 g) was suspended in methylene chloride (45 mL) in a nitrogen atmosphere followed by addition of triethylamine (40 mmol, 4.04 g, 5.6 mL) with constant stirring. After the color changed to orangish yellow, a solution of phosphorus trichloride (10 mmol, 1.36 g, 0.9 mL) in methylene chloride (25 mL) was added dropwise with stirring. The stirring was continued for 5–20 h till the reaction was complete, as indicated by ³¹P NMR spectroscopy. The solvent was removed thereafter under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 40 mL). The combined extracts were concentrated to one third of their volume and left in a refrigerator at 0–5 °C whereupon a yellow orange solid of 3a deposited which was separated and dried under vacuum. In case of 3b, the product obtained was a sticky mass and could not be crystallized.

1,3-Bis(methoxycarbonyl)-7-ethyl-1,3-aza-phospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridine (3a) :

Yield 56%, m.p. 140–142 °C (Found : C, 55.27; H, 5.21; N, 4.92. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄NO₄P (279.3) : C, 55.91; H, 5.05; N, 5.01%); δ ³¹P NMR (CDCl₃) : 179.6; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm) : 1.20 (3H, t, *J*_{HH} 8.4 Hz, 7-CH₂CH₃), 2.66 (2H, q, *J*_{HH} 8.4 Hz, 7-CH₂CH₃), 3.86 (6H, s, OCH₃), 6.80 (1H, dd, *J*_{HH} 8.2 Hz, ⁴*J*_{HH} < 1.0 Hz, 6-H), 8.46 (1H, s, 8-H), 9.70 (1H, d, *J*_{HH} 8.2 Hz, 5-H).

1,3-Bis(ethoxycarbonyl)-7-ethyl-1,3-azaphosphol[1,5-a]pyridine (3b) :

Yield 35%, sticky mass; $\delta^{31}\text{P}$ NMR (CDCl_3) : 179.3; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 1.22 (3H, t, J_{HH} 8.5 Hz, 7- CH_2CH_3), 1.29 (6H, t, J_{HH} 7.0 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 2.72 (2H, q, J_{HH} 8.5 Hz, 7- CH_2CH_3), 4.34 (4H, q, J_{HH} 7.0 Hz, OCH_2), 6.90 (1H, dd, J_{HH} 7.0 Hz, $^4J_{\text{HH}} < 1.0$ Hz, 6-H), 8.55 (1H, s, 8-H), 9.76 (1H, d, J_{HH} 7.0 Hz, 5-H).

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References

1. H. Neumaier, in "Methoden der Organischen Chemie (Houben-Weyl)", ed. M. Regitz, Vol. E1: 'Organische Phosphor - Verbindungen I', Georg Thieme Verlag, Stuttgart, 1982, p. 276.
2. P. Pellon and J. Hamelin, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 5611.
3. I. F. Lutsenko, *Z. Chem.*, 1984, **24**, 345.
4. R. K. Bansal, K. Karaghiosoff, N. Gupta, A. Schmidpeter and C. Spindler, *Chem. Ber.*, 1991, **124**, 475.
5. R. K. Bansal, N. Gupta, R. Gupta, G. Pandey and M. Agarwal, *Phosphorus Sulfur Silicon*, 1996, **112**, 121.
6. R. K. Bansal, A. Surana and N. Gupta, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 1565.
7. R. K. Bansal, N. Gupta, M. Baweja, L. Hemrajani and V. K. Jain, *Heteroatom. Chem.*, 2001, **12**, 602.
8. A. Schmidpeter and G. Jochem, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1992, **33**, 471.
9. R. K. Bansal, L. Hemrajani and N. Gupta, *Heteroatom. Chem.*, 1999, **10**, 598.
10. O. I. Kolodyazhnyi, "Phosphorus Ylides. Chemistry and Application in Organic Synthesis", Wiley-VCH Publishers, Weinheim, New York, Chichester, 1999.